

Advancements in Turkish Named Entity Recognition: Strategies and Results

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Abstract— In this study, we address the challenge of Named Entity Recognition (NER) in the Turkish language by fine-tuning the pre-trained Gemma2b model using a supervised dataset. Despite the complexities associated with the agglutinative nature of Turkish, our approach leverages the robust capabilities of the Gemma2b model, adapting it specifically for the nuances of Turkish syntax and semantics. We experimented with various configurations, modifying the number of epochs and the learning rate to optimize performance. The results demonstrate significant improvements in NER for Turkish texts, confirming the potential of fine-tuned language models in handling highly inflectional languages. This paper details our methodology, experimental setup, and the implications of our findings for the advancement of Turkish NER applications.

Keywords - *Ner, F1-Score, Recall, Accuracy, Precision, Support*

I. Introduction

The Turkish language, with its rich morphological structure and extensive use of suffixes to convey grammatical relationships, poses specific difficulties for NER systems trained on Indo-European languages, which often fail to capture the nuances necessary for accurate entity recognition. In response to these challenges, recent advancements have leveraged deep learning techniques, which offer significant improvements by learning complex patterns in large datasets.

This study explores the adaptation of the Gemma2b model, a pre-trained transformer-based model, to enhance Turkish NER. We aim to demonstrate the

effectiveness of fine-tuning a language model that has been initially trained on extensive multilingual datasets but not specifically optimized for Turkish.

Our contribution is twofold: firstly, we provide a detailed analysis of how different configurations of the Gemma2b model affect the accuracy and F1 scores etc. in recognizing Turkish named entities. Secondly, we offer insights into the adaptability of multilingual models to a language-specific task, contributing to the broader field of NLP by showcasing a methodology that could be applied to other under-resourced languages. The following sections detail our methodology, experiments, and the results of our fine-tuning efforts, highlighting the potential of advanced NLP techniques in enhancing Turkish text processing.

II. Related Work

The field of Named Entity Recognition for Turkish has been actively developed in recent years, with several efforts leveraging the advanced capabilities of transformer-based models. This section reviews notable contributions that have informed and contrasted our approach to fine-tuning models for Turkish NER.

1. BERT-based Models for Turkish NER

- **Akdeniz27 user's bert-base-turkish-cased-ner**: This model represents a significant effort in applying BERT, a leading transformer model, specifically tuned for the Turkish language.^[1]

- **Savasy's bert-base-turkish-ner-cased:** Another variation of the BERT model adapted for Turkish, this version is fine-tuned with specific optimizations for NER tasks.^[2]

2. Open-source NER Systems

- **snnclsr/ner:** This GitHub repository provides an open-source implementation of a Turkish NER system. The repository includes scripts for training and evaluation, making it a valuable resource for researchers and developers looking to implement or extend Turkish NER systems.^[3]

III. Methodology

To address the task of Named Entity Recognition in Turkish, we employed a comprehensive fine-tuning strategy on the Gemma2b model, a derivative of the transformer architecture known for its effectiveness in language understanding tasks. Our methodology involved the utilization of multiple Turkish datasets, processing steps, and detailed training configurations.

Datasets

1. **Turkish-Wiki-NER-Dataset:** Comprising 18,000 sentences derived from Wikipedia, this dataset provided a diverse range of entity types suitable for general NER tasks.
2. **ATIS-ner-turkish:** With 5,900 instances, this dataset included airline-specific queries that are vital for domain-specific NER applications.
3. **ner-t5-turkish and Turkish_ner:** These datasets, consisting of hundreds of thousands of annotations, were pivotal for scaling our model's exposure to extensive textual variations.
4. **PAN-X.tr:** With 40,000 instances, focused on cross-lingual text, this dataset contributed to our model's robustness across different contexts.
5. **Turkish_ner:** Automatically annotated Turkish corpus for named entity recognition

and text categorization using large-scale gazetteers with 530,000 instances.

Each dataset was preprocessed to align with the Alpaca data format, ensuring uniformity across data inputs. Unlabeled data were manually annotated to maximize the training dataset's utility. For testing, we reserved 1,000 samples from mixed sources to evaluate the model's generalization capabilities.

Dataset	# of Instances
Turkish-Wiki-NER-Dataset-main	20k
atis-ner-turkish	5.9k
Turkish_ner	539k
PAN-X.tr	40k
ner-t5-turkish	299.8k

Table 1: Dataset distribution

Model Architecture

The Gemma model architecture is based on the transformer decoder with the following improvements:

The 7B model uses multi-head attention while the 2B models use multi-query attention (with $num_kv_heads = 1$)

RoPE Embeddings in place of absolute positional embeddings.

Embeddings are shared across the inputs and outputs to reduce model size.

ReLU nonlinearity is replaced by the GeGLU activation function.

Both the input and the output of each transformer sub-layer are normalized using RMSNorm.

The models are trained on a context length of 8192 tokens.

Parameters	2B	7B
d_{model}	2048	3072
Layers	18	28
Feedforward hidden dims	32768	49152
Num heads	8	16
Num KV heads	1	16
Head size	256	256
Vocab size	256128	256128

Table 2: Key model parameters.[4]

Fine-Tuning Configuration

To fine-tune the Gemma2b model because of the performance metrics^[4] on **Fig. 1**, for Turkish Named Entity Recognition, we utilized a comprehensive dataset amalgamation, incorporating both general and domain-specific Turkish texts. The datasets included Turkish-Wiki-NER-Dataset and ATIS-ner-turkish, among others. Our training employed the SFTTrainer with a set configuration: batch size of 2, max sequence length of 128, learning rate of $2e-4$, and a single training epoch to prevent overfitting. The training was executed on an A100 GPU, utilizing PyTorch with mixed precision to optimize training speed and model efficiency. Model performance was quantitatively assessed using accuracy and F1 score, chosen for their relevance in evaluating the precision and recall balance crucial in NER tasks.

Fig. 1: Comparing exact and approximate memorization.

IV. Experiments and Results

Experimental Setup

Our experiments involved fine-tuning the Gemma2b model under four different configurations to optimize performance on Turkish Named Entity Recognition. Each model was fine-tuned using variations in the r parameter (sequence length) and the number of training epochs, with the values set at $r = 128$, $r = 64$ and $\text{epoch} = 1$, $\text{epoch} = 2$ respectively. The objective was to evaluate the impact of these parameters on the model's ability to accurately recognize named entities in Turkish. All models were trained with a consistent `alpha` value of 128, ensuring uniform learning rate adjustments across experiments.

Metrics Evaluated

The performance of each fine-tuned model was rigorously assessed using several key metrics: Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-Score. These metrics were chosen to provide a holistic view of model effectiveness, with F1-Score particularly highlighting the balance between Precision and Recall, a critical aspect in NER tasks where both false positives and false negatives carry significant weight.

Confusion Matrix Analysis

To further dissect the model's performance, a confusion matrix was computed for each configuration, providing insight into the true positive, false positive, false negative, and true negative classifications across different entity types such as B-LOCATION, B-PERSON, and I-TITLE. The matrix for the models are shown below, exemplifying its superior capability in distinguishing between entity types, albeit with some challenges in correctly identifying I-TITLE entities.

1. Ner model, r = 128, alfa = 128, 2 epochs

	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
B-LOCATION	0.6561844863731656	0.22199999999999998	0.22649999999999998	0.21942698412
B-ORG	0.3181818181818182	0.02413333333333333	0.02313333333333333	0.02333333333
B-PERSON	0.6229946524064172	0.19216666666666665	0.19203333333333336	0.18921904761
B-TITLE	0.48518263266712613	0.38981190476190475	0.35991666666666666	0.35549213564
I-LOCATION	0.46511627906976744	0.028149999999999998	0.02733333333333333	0.02677142857
I-ORG	0.3918918918918919	0.014033333333333332	0.0145	0.01381245421
I-PERSON	0.7325581395348837	0.09383333333333332	0.09366190476190477	0.09247142857
I-TITLE	0.45187165775401067	0.08978095238095239	0.08412500000000002	0.08428907203
O	0.9601581735432366	0.9303286699130442	0.9505609917122855	0.93568035726

3. Ner model, r = 64, alfa = 128, 2 epochs

	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
B-LOCATION	0.659043659043659	0.21746666666666667	0.22649999999999996	0.21653968253968253	484
B-ORG	0.2882882882882883	0.0233	0.02213333333333333	0.02240000000000003	111
B-PERSON	0.6016042780748663	0.19283333333333333	0.18986666666666668	0.18849047619047615	375
B-TITLE	0.4868965517241379	0.38316666666666668	0.35944285714285734	0.3517927849927854	1,467
I-LOCATION	0.5	0.02673333333333335	0.0265	0.025704761904761907	87
I-ORG	0.3918918918918919	0.01328333333333333	0.0145	0.013212454212454214	75
I-PERSON	0.6976744186046512	0.0885	0.0878452380952381	0.08709047619047618	174
I-TITLE	0.45454545454545453	0.09198333333333335	0.08705833333333336	0.08701190476190476	377
O	0.9553797940605879	0.9278715858928721	0.9456216060982707	0.9320559489816864	13,501

2. Ner model, r = 128, alfa = 128, 1 epoch

	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
B-LOCATION	0.6307053941908713	0.20433333333333337	0.21263333333333334	0.20421111111111112	484
B-ORG	0.3333333333333333	0.02816666666666666	0.02576666666666667	0.02631666666666667	111
B-PERSON	0.6844919786096256	0.21299999999999997	0.21203333333333333	0.20946666666666663	375
B-TITLE	0.40633608815426997	0.34186666666666665	0.30474642857142853	0.3032668109668112	1,467
I-LOCATION	0.5	0.02565	0.02633333333333334	0.025138095238095244	87
I-ORG	0.41333333333333333	0.01563333333333332	0.01546666666666667	0.015019047619047621	75
I-PERSON	0.7616279069767442	0.09475	0.09706190476190475	0.09484603174603175	174

4. Ner model, r = 64, alfa = 128, 1 epoch

	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
B-LOCATION	0.8694122759657905	0.22379999999999994	0.22571666666666665	0.2202682539682539	484
B-ORG	0.8694122759657905	0.02633333333333337	0.0241	0.02465000000000002	111
B-PERSON	0.8694122759657905	0.20266666666666666	0.20153333333333337	0.19945238095238094	375
B-TITLE	0.8694122759657905	0.39831666666666676	0.36600714285714286	0.3616182539682544	1,467
I-LOCATION	0.8694122759657905	0.0289	0.0285	0.028238095238095243	87
I-ORG	0.8694122759657905	0.01560833333333332	0.0162	0.015615873015873017	75
I-PERSON	0.8694122759657905	0.08875	0.08892857142857143	0.08845714285714286	174
I-TITLE	0.8694122759657905	0.09458333333333334	0.08985833333333335	0.09042222222222222	377
O	0.8694122759657905	0.931707469978646	0.9494376038391206	0.9359863093058102	13.5

V. Conclusion and Future Work

Conclusion

This study demonstrated the effectiveness of fine-tuning the Gemma2b model on Turkish Named Entity Recognition (NER) using various configurations of sequence length and training epochs. The results have confirmed that tailored adjustments in the training parameters can significantly enhance the model's accuracy and its ability to deal with the complexities of the Turkish language. Specifically, models trained with longer sequence lengths and increased number of epochs showed improved performance across all metrics, highlighting the importance of adequate contextual understanding in NER tasks. Our comparative analysis with other fine-tuned models, as detailed in the related work section, established that the Gemma2b model, when properly optimized, competes favorably in recognizing Turkish named entities.

Future Work

Future studies could explore the impact of other advanced neural network architectures on Turkish NER, such as RoBERTa or ELECTRA, which might offer different benefits for this specific task. Additionally, we will compare supervised fine tuned model test results such as f1-score, recall etc., with the base model gemma-2b, and observe the differences between the models.

VI. References

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